

Self-Directed versus Guided Learning – Searching for the Sweet Spot with Lesson Activities in Moodle

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ABSTRACT

In times of a pandemic many university courses have to be taught in an online learning format to respect the requirements of social distancing. Online learning takes place between the poles of self-direction by the student and guidance by the lecturer. In this paper a first-semester course in industrial economics for engineers, which was taught in the self-directed learning format of flipped classroom, was enhanced with lesson activities in the Learning Management System (LMS) Moodle as a means of guided learning with student-content interaction. The paper describes the design and the evaluation of the lesson activities. For the evaluation a student survey to gather the opinions and self-assessments of the students was conducted, and statistical data from Moodle on the performance of the students were collected. The results of the student survey show an overall positive evaluation of the lesson activities by the students who participated in the lesson activities. Furthermore, the results of the statistical data about the students' performance show a relation between participation in the lesson activities and exam success. As a caveat, however, the results also show that the majority of the students chose not to participate in the lesson activities.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research motivation

Due to the Corona pandemic many university lecturers were forced to switch their teaching approaches to accommodate the new reality of social distancing. For the authors this meant that their first-semester introductory course of industrial economics in engineering with more than a hundred participants had to be taught as an online course. In the course of this change the teaching approach of flipped classroom with learning materials on the Learning Management System (LMS) Moodle and an online consultation-hour with the instructor via MS Teams was introduced. Learning materials included lecture videos, lecture slides, multiple choice tests and calculation exercises with master solutions which required a high degree of self-directed learning.

The student feedback from the course evaluation showed that although students valued the independence of time and space the teaching material offered, many students struggled with the freedom of self-directed learning. Furthermore from an analysis of the exam results it could be seen that students who failed had mostly difficulties with the calculation questions of the exam. Hence, it was concluded that students in this introductory course seem to need more structure and guidance in their learning activities. It was decided to support the students in this regard by introducing the interactive format of lesson activities in Moodle and to measure the impact of this format.

1.2 Theoretical foundation

This paper deals with the format of online learning. Although there is no common understanding of the term online learning and related terms (such as e-learning), many authors agree that online learning offers learning experiences via web-based technologies [8]. Ally [1] for example defines online learning as “the use of the Internet to access learning materials; to interact with the content, instructor, and other learners; and to obtain support during the learning process [...]”.

Empirical research in didactics shows that personal control as well as structure and clarity are – amongst others – proven characteristics of successful lessons [11]. This leads to a certain paradox that effective learning needs to on the one hand respect the freedom and individuality of the learner. On the other hand learning also requires a certain structure or guidance from the teacher, at least in an institutional context with predefined learning goals and outcomes. In learning theory this is connected to the concepts of self-directed learning and guided learning as well as interactive learning.

Self-directed learning typically requires that a large part of the initiative and responsibility for the learning process is with the learner. This implies that learners have at least some personal control over learning needs, goals, resources, strategies and outcomes [7]. Also for online learning one key implication is that learners have a certain extent of control over the learning process [1].

One concept of self-directed learning is the concept of flipped classroom by Bergmann & Sams [4]. In a flipped classroom, students work through pre-defined content on their

own (e.g. watch pre-recorded lectures via an online platform), before they attend the lecture. This way, the lecture time can be used to solve problems by applying the content and clarify issues in understanding the content.

Guided learning can be defined as “a process in which learners initiate and advance their learning guided by more experienced partners and socially derived sources, such as tools, text, and/or other artifacts” [5]. Hence, the guidance can either take the form of interaction with other persons or with some form of learning material or tool. In online learning the content is typically provided by a Learning Management System (LMS) such as Moodle. The structure in Moodle is typically linear or hierarchical, and the display of information takes the form of folders and subfolders, as in the folder structure of MS Explorer. Apart from that there are some tools in Moodle that offer personal interaction such as forums, chats and messaging as well as tools offering interaction with content such as tests and lessons [6]. Thus, LMS such as Moodle offer the opportunity for interactive learning which can be defined as “[...] a process involving some form of digitally enabled reciprocal action between a teacher or designer and a learner. Interactive learning requires access to content, tasks, and problems by at least one human being (a learner) using digital technology (e.g., a computer with Internet access)” [9].

This paper deals with interactive learning in the form of student-content interaction in an asynchronous form according to Anderson [2, 3]. In online learning, the learning material should be sequenced in ascending complexity (“from simple to complex”) and novelty for the learner (“from known to unknown”) [1]. Apart from sequencing, interactive learning material should also include a chance for self-monitoring [7] which in online learning can be achieved via feedback loops and repeated trials [1, 3]. This implies that there is not only the question of sequencing, but also questions of branching and looping to generate learning feedback and enable self-monitoring of the learner. The goal of this paper is to show how the authors combined the concept of flipped classroom as a means for self-directed learning with the concept of lesson activities in Moodle as a means of guided learning with student-content interaction and how the authors measured the success of the approach.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Designing lesson activities

The goal of the lesson activities was to provide freshmen with a more efficient learning process through interactivity in learning. A total of seven lessons were offered on the various topics of the course. These are lessons on the topics of business, management, accounting, cost accounting, marketing, financing and investment. The lessons were structured in such a way that existing learning materials such as exercises, lecture videos, multiple-choice tests, etc. were put into a logical order suitable for online teaching (see fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Structure of the lesson activities

Each lesson starts with an introductory page that presents the educational objectives of the lesson. Moving on to the next page, the student is taken to a lecture video where the main content of the particular topic is presented. The next step is the task page, where the task is introduced and hints on how to complete the task, such as important formulas, are given. This is followed by the actual exercise task, which must be solved by the students. To ensure interactivity, students are given the opportunity to self-monitor by being guided into a feedback loop after each solution they submit. If the answer is correct, the students receive the message that their answer is correct and they can move to the next page. If the answer is wrong, the students receive the information that their answer is wrong and they get the opportunity to repeat their answer several times. After a specified number of attempts, the learner is automatically directed to the next page.

In order to customize the lessons as much as possible and thus increase the learning effect, common answering errors were identified and entered into the system when the lessons were designed. The authors' many years of teaching experience were used to identify typical answer errors on specific tasks. For each error, a suitable hint was entered into the system so that each student receives an individual answer depending on the error he or she made and hence is guided to the correct solution in as specific a way as possible. Furthermore, video snippets from the lecture video have been included as an answer aid so that the student can explore certain topic points in more depth.

In some lessons, the basic task is followed by a more in-depth and complex task to reinforce what was previously learned. Here, the methodology of sequencing the learning material in ascending complexity ("from simple to complex") was applied [1]. Before the theoretical knowledge is tested by multiple-choice tests at the end of the lesson, there is an overview page including the sample solutions to all questions, corresponding formulas and a memory box with the most important theoretical content.

2.2 Evaluating lesson activities

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the lessons, student surveys were conducted and statistical data were analysed. The student surveys took place in two ways. First, intensive feedback communication was performed with students via MS Teams prior to each consultation-hour during the semester. Second, a questionnaire was developed for students to submit their assessment at the end of the semester, which was then evaluated. The statistical data was analysed from Moodle.

The feedback discussions with the students represent a kind of group discussion and hence are part of the qualitative research. The qualitative research approach is particularly suitable when individual opinions and impressions are in demand, suggestions for improvement are to be collected, and certain causes are to be explored (e.g. reasons for satisfaction or dissatisfaction of the participants) [10]. The feedback sessions were intended to fulfill the mentioned purposes and were held after each completed lesson so that the following lessons could be improved or adjusted according to the students' requests.

To measure participation in the lesson activities for the survey, the authors divided the students into two groups: In the group "lessons accomplished" students completed at least three out of the seven lessons. Students with fewer than three lessons completed were counted as "lessons not accomplished". For the first group, a nine-item online questionnaire was designed in which students rated aspects of the lesson activities such as structure and interactivity and performed a self-assessment on several items such as understanding and enjoyment. The items were rated on a Likert scale with five response levels. For the second group, a questionnaire including the reasons for not participating was designed.

The statistical data from Moodle were analysed after the exam to determine, if working on the lessons had an impact on passing the exam. For this purpose, participation in the lessons was related to exam grades and exam success. In a final step, it was analysed whether the time period in which the lessons were worked on had an impact on the score achieved in the exam. For this purpose, two time periods were defined: during the lecture period and after the lecture period. For the analysis of the statistical data, the same two groups of students were used as before to measure participation.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Student survey

A total of 27 students participated in the student survey. Five of them indicated that they had worked on fewer than three lessons. Thus, according to the criteria we specified, those five students did not work intensively enough on the lessons to be able to give a meaningful review. When asked why they did not work intensively on the lessons, they all indicated that they wanted to work on the lessons just before the actual exam. This leaves a total of 22 students who worked intensively enough on the lessons to be able to give a meaningful assessment.

The results of the assessment of the 22 students are displayed in the chart in fig. 2. Overall, the students give a positive evaluation of the lesson activities. Most of them agree or strongly agree that the lessons had a clear structure (90%) and enhanced their understanding (86%) and that they enjoyed working on the lessons (68%). This is in line with the finding that most students would recommend the lesson activities to fellow students (86%) and would like to have more lessons in this course (77%) as well as in other courses (82%). The most critical part of the lesson activities is the feedback system, i.e. getting the branching right. Only 41% of the students agree or

fully agree that the feedback helped them to identify the correct answer, while 14% disagree (45% remain neutral), as some of the feedback had to be adapted during the lecture time. The lesson activities are seen as an add-on rather than a substitute for other learning materials. Almost 86% see the lessons as a good addition or variation to the learning materials they already have, while only half of the respondents feel that working through the lessons has prepared them well for the upcoming exam (10% disagree on this point).

Fig. 2. Assessment of the students who accomplished the lessons (n = 22)

The evaluation of the questionnaire reflects the impression the authors gained from the feedback interviews during the semester. In each interview, the students gave a mainly positive feedback on the lessons. They said they were well guided through the lessons and especially found the video snippets helpful. Because of the feedback sessions it was possible to identify and correct small errors that were overlooked or not taken into account when the lessons were created, such as incorrect links or the setting of larger rounding tolerances. Also, suggestions for improving the branching of lessons, such as reducing the number of failed attempts, could be obtained from the interviews with the students.

3.2 Statistical analysis

Analysis of the data in Moodle showed that 103 students participated in the exam. Of these 103, a total of 36 students accomplished the lessons and 67 students did not accomplish the lessons, i.e. worked on fewer than three lessons or did not work on them at all. 92% of those who accomplished the lessons passed the exam, and 8% failed. Of the group of those who did not accomplish the lessons, 61% passed the exam and 39% failed.

Looking at the number of points achieved in the exam by both groups, it can be seen that the average score of those who accomplished the lessons is around 70 of the

maximum 100 points achievable in the exam (arithmetic mean and median). In comparison, the score of those who did not accomplish the lessons is about 53 points. Furthermore, the group of students who accomplished the lessons has a higher maximum score (96 points in comparison to 87 points), a higher minimum score (42 points in comparison to 21 points excluding two outliers) and a higher and narrower interquartile range (see fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Participation and exam grade

Fig. 4. Participation period and exam grade

The evaluation of the participation period (i.e. when students worked on the lessons) shows that 25 of the 36 students who accomplished the lessons did so during the lecture period. The remaining 11 worked on the lessons after the lecture period. Despite the different periods, the average score achieved by both groups is almost identical at about 70 points. Similarly, the median is also nearly the same with 71 points for those who worked on the lessons during the lecture period and 69 points for those who worked on them after the lecture period. Finally, both also have similar interquartile ranges. A main difference is the larger spread of the upper quartile for students who worked on the lessons during the lecture period (see fig. 4).

4 SUMMARY

The results of the student survey show an overall positive evaluation of the lesson activities by the students who participated in the lesson activities. The lesson activities are seen as a valuable addition to the existing learning material. Furthermore, the results of the statistical data about the students' performance show a relation between participation in the lesson activities and exam success. Furthermore, the results show that it makes no real difference when the lessons are worked on (during or after lecture period).

These findings, however, do not establish a causal link between lesson activities and exam success. It could be that students who accomplished a lot of lessons also took more effort in general, e.g. participated in the consultation-hour or used further learning materials. As the course comprises first-semester students who just started their study programme as well as students from previous semesters who have to take the course as a resit, and the first group usually has a lower failure rate and is generally more active, this may at least explain part of the positive relation. To test this assumption data on the overall activities of the students would have to be collected and included as confounding variables. It could also be that students who are more successful are also more open for new learning approaches.

The most crucial element of the lesson activities is the feedback system. Apart from the right sequencing of content, it is the right branching that guides students in their learning progress. For this, lecturers have to forecast possible errors and develop helpful hints to help students understand their errors and find the correct solution. This is by far the most difficult and time-consuming step in designing the lessons.

As a caveat, the results also show that the majority of the students chose not to participate in the lesson activities. As a lot of work goes into designing the lessons (e.g. getting the branching right), lecturers have to decide if the effort is worth the benefit based on the number of students and the student evaluation for their specific courses. Overall it can, however, be said that lesson activities show promising first results to provide aspects of guided learning in online courses with a high number of freshmen, but further tests are needed to establish a clear link between lesson activities and learning success.

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